

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY IS THE BASIS OF PROFESSIONAL MASTERY OF THE TEACHER IS AN INDICATOR

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Abstract

The article presents the theoretical and technological bases of the implementation of pedagogical activity functions (the application of pedagogical activity and communication skills) aimed at transforming the expected results of the educator into the personality qualities of the students in the teaching process. The modern school requires from us teachers who can perfectly deal with the education of the young generation, pedagogical personalities who have risen to the heights of pedagogical mastery. This makes the problem of pedagogical mastery even more relevant for modern educational theory and practice. The object of pedagogical work is a living human being, an active being with unique individual qualities, a personal attitude and understanding of the happenings. In the research work for the realization of pedagogical activity, the teaching profession, general, special and specific requirements for this profession, pedagogical activity and its subsystems, pedagogical skills, pedagogical abilities, pedagogical mastery, pedagogical communication, forms of communication, teacher-student cooperation, and its forms are discussed. Generalizations were made based on the "system-structure" approach and the "opportunity-movement-new quality" paradigm.

Keywords: Pedagogical professionalism; pedagogical communication; forms of pedagogical communication; forms of cooperation; teaching profession; innovations; scientific pedagogy; skills and habits; pedagogical process; portfolio; pedagogical awareness.

Relevance of the research topic. Pedagogical mastery is the professional mastery of persons engaged in educational activities - teachers and tutors. It is a high level of pedagogical activity, the highest and constantly improving art of education. Methodological mastery is a synthesis of scientific knowledge, skills, habits and personal activity of the teacher. The main essence of this work lies in the personality of the teacher, his position, ability to manage his activities at a high professional level. In addition, the teacher should be aware of the pedagogical activity, take into account its purpose, means, object, and subject. For this reason, I have taken into account that the level of pedagogical professionalism of the teacher must be constantly monitored, so this issue is always relevant.

Interpretation of research materials. If the object of pedagogic science is the process of imparting experience, its subject is the study of the object from a pedagogical point of view, then the subject of pedagogical mastery is the process of studying that object with more skill and perfection. A teacher striving to rise to the level of pedagogical mastery should know the pedagogical processes, its components, composition, and scope in detail and precisely. It is at this time that it becomes possible to rise to the peak of mastery by transforming the system of knowledge, the system of skills and habits, from reality to idealism in the field of creative experience. A master is a person who does his work skillfully. A master teacher is a deep connoisseur of the psychology of a person and how to teach him, he is a person who has mastered the ways of training. The activity of the teacher should be aimed at training harmoniously formed, free, enterprising, hardworking, nationally zealous, Islamic spiritual, cultured individuals

who can meet the demands of today's and future development of the society. Pedagogical awareness, skill, mastery shows itself.[3;42]

Pedagogical professionalism, as a socio-cultural phenomenon, is the teacher's professional activity masterfully, on scientific grounds, understanding the social status of his profession and applying innovations in his activity. The basis of pedagogical professionalism is laid in the process of initial professional education, and it is updated, developed, formed in the process of the teacher's entire professional activity, and becomes even more perfect with the emergence of new qualities. Although the teacher's pedagogical activity has a single goal at all times, its content, conditions of realization, principles, and methods have been constantly changing and developing. They were innovative, innovative teachers who performed their work at a high level and gained a great reputation for their professionalism. True teachers love their profession and strive to make it even better. The teacher bringing innovations to his activity, applying advanced practice or innovations has led to the improvement and development of pedagogical professionalism itself. Therefore, pedagogical professionalism has been constantly developing as a pedagogical activity, and teacher professionalism has become an indicator that characterizes the work of individual teachers, distinguishes it from others, and makes it more perfect. [14;78]

Professional performance of the teacher's pedagogical activity is characterized by a number of indicators. All this becomes one of the main factors of his success as a professional. These factors mainly consist of:

1. To understand the high mission and responsibility of the title of teacher. Every teacher, even during his school years, when he shows interest in this profession, must realize that the title of teacher is high and responsible, that the teacher fulfills a fateful mission. He should accept as a life belief that the teacher is indebted to the society, to the citizens, and that his life is connected to this profession in order to fulfill this civic duty with dignity. He should know that the future of our country and society depends on its economy, economic power, and above all on the teacher, the level of teachers' activity in building a new society, and how to educate today's children. A teacher does not have the right to be negligent in his work, not to do some action that he should do, not to do some work that he should do. This right, being both a moral and a legal right, is related to the teacher taking on a great mission before the society. The state and people whose teachers are illiterate, irresponsible, who do not understand or do not want to do what they are doing for the society, the people, the nation cannot have a bright future. Since teachers spread this light, society cannot develop if every teacher, whether young or old, does not understand this.

2. Interest, love and passion for teaching, teaching profession. The observations made show that the attitude towards this profession and teaching is not the same not only in secondary schools, but even among teachers working at higher levels and levels of education. Some of them (unfortunately, their number is not much more than the latter) work in this profession with great enthusiasm, they act with real pleasure in their profession and do not imagine their life outside of teaching. They live with this profession, they are proud of it. It is clear that such teachers are constantly trying to work better in order to move forward, perform better and improve their professionalism. Another part of the teachers are those who are not interested in this profession, and work only for the sake of getting a salary. Teaching is a profession that requires self-love and enthusiasm. When these things happen, there is success and progress. These motivate the teacher to work on himself, master the secrets of his profession, and guide him to competence and professionalism. When a teacher loves his profession, he does not complain about its difficulties, but instead looks for ways to overcome these difficulties, and goes to his daily meetings with students not with old knowledge, but with new information, richer knowledge, and innovations that can surprise children. The love of the profession and specialty prompts the teacher to move forward and create new motives. Our society has reached such a level of development that it is impossible to surprise students with the knowledge, skills and habits that teachers have acquired in higher schools. If a few years ago, the main source of information in the learning process was the teacher, now these sources have increased so much that it is not easy to create enthusiasm for reading and learning in students and to stimulate them in learning activities. For this, the teacher's love and emphasis on his art and profession is necessary. Then he will be able to search, learn and teach students.

3. To love one's specialty, to constantly enrich it with innovations. Not only the teaching profession, but also the teacher's love for his specialty is united with his interest in constantly enriching it. No matter what specialty he has, if the teacher likes him, he will try to bring the related innovations and innovations to his activities and increase his knowledge. Experience shows that a teacher's wealth of specialties, deep knowledge of his specialty, and his love for it increase children's love and interest in this specialty. Yakomensky, the founder of scientific pedagogy, wrote that a teacher who does not love his profession, the subject he teaches, is a shadow without a body, a cloud without rain, a lamp without light. A teacher who loves his science and the subject he teaches, who always works, is a tree that grows on its own roots, is nourished by its own juice, and therefore constantly grows, turns green, blossoms, and bears fruit. A good teacher opens the consciousness of students, not with water flowing from other rivers, but opens the fountain of knowledge hidden in the student's mind and waters it with its water. A teacher should be an example of simplicity in work and dress, cheerfulness and industriousness in his activities, modesty and good morals in behavior, the art of speaking and silence in speech, and intelligence in public life. Enriching the teacher's specialty with innovations is a proven means of increasing children's interest in reading and learning. Just as a honey bee gathers nectar from thousands of flowers and gathers honey, so does a teacher, as he takes from each innovation and source an innovation that he considers suitable for him, his knowledge increases and becomes richer. When these are applied to practical activities, professionalism increases and improves. The teacher should never be confident in his previous knowledge, he should not come to class unprepared saying "I know this". He should think about the lessons he will take and try to make them meaningful. He should correctly determine the main argument and content line of the topics he will be studying, try to build his lesson on that line, and achieve result-oriented education. He should imagine the lesson in advance and then implement it.

4. Love for children, enjoy working with them. Love for children is an axiom that does not need any proof, without which it is possible to be neither a good teacher nor a good educator. The fact that the teacher can enjoy the smile on the children's faces when entering the classroom, their interest in learning and knowing, not only motivates him to work better, to perform creative activities, but also increases the optimality of the pedagogical process as a criterion of professionalism and competence. When the teacher's love for his profession is combined with his love for the student, their synthesis guides the teacher to success and elevates him to perfection.

5. To have a professional conscience and a civic position. Conscience is the judge inside everyone, who keeps him under constant control and does not allow him to make mistakes. Professional conscience is like that. The fact that a teacher has a professional conscience creates such a positive energy, a fertile field within him that always motivates the teacher to perform the difficult and responsible task with dignity and honor

without any negligence. As if like a supervisor, he constantly demands a report from the teacher about his work. A good teacher always improves his professionalism by working on himself to get rid of this report. The fact that a teacher has a civic position means that he does his work not only for remuneration or to promote himself as a good teacher, but for the prosperity of the people, country, and nation to which he belongs, and that their future is in safe hands. A teacher should not forget that he lays a cornerstone for the foundation of the future with every lesson and extracurricular activity. This feature is also of great importance for the influence of the teacher's personality on the students. The students who sit in front of the teacher today are the owners of tomorrow. Today's students will work tomorrow in different parts of the country, in different fields. Therefore, the teacher should never forget that the future of the society is directly proportional to the training, education and upbringing they give today.

6. To increase knowledge, skills and habits by constantly working on oneself. The famous Russian pedagogue K.D.Ushinsky has a famous saying that a teacher dies when he stops studying and working on himself. It is true. Time is constantly moving forward, information is increasing rapidly, and sometimes the children receive more information than the teacher. Rapid information fields are emerging in all fields of science, so that the teacher can acquire them, connect them with the pedagogical process, and apply the innovations to his own activity. It is impossible to imagine a modern teacher without them. This is an activity that not only makes the teacher work on himself, but also increases the acquired knowledge and enriches the skills and habits. A teacher should always take care of self-development. He should be able to convey his knowledge and skills to the goal of education, to the modern tasks facing him, to improve himself by acquiring new knowledge, modern training and education methods. Without them, it is impossible to become a professional teacher and acquire certain skills. New knowledge and competences are acquired when continuous, continuous and lifelong education becomes the criterion for teachers.

7. Mastering pedagogical techniques. Mastering pedagogical techniques is one of the important criteria for teacher professionalism. A teacher who has pedagogical technique is a teacher who is able to perform his profession skillfully, professionally and competently. In the pedagogical process, there are sometimes neglected but subtle techniques that often prevent the teacher from approaching the pedagogical process professionally and lowers the teacher's professionalism. [13;76]

If necessary, he should deliberately make certain mistakes, check how he affects the students, and check how the lesson he is passing affects the children. Words like "you don't know that", "you didn't say it correctly" should never be said to the child, it is necessary to try to make them understand the mistakes made based on the answers of other students and the corrections made. "Do you understand?" - rather than the expression, "Did I understand?" - has a greater impact on the students, so this expression makes the teacher more authoritative in

the eyes of the students. Pedagogical professionalism creates a whole system by linking all these subtleties of the teacher's activity together like a chain. Thus, by summarizing the above, it can be said that the professional qualities that a teacher should have are as follows: [11;148]

The teacher should know:

- state and government directives and directives about schools, teachers and education;
- the field of science he acquired and his specialty;
- age and individual characteristics of children;
- the science of pedagogy and psychology;
- the basics of modern pedagogical technologies;
- intra-disciplinary and interdisciplinary integration;
- children's literature.

The teacher should be able to:

- to be able to teach and clearly explain what they think;
- managing the class;
- to respect the child's personality;
- skillfully use the educational function of training;
- truthfulness in words and correctness in behavior;
- to educate;
- to develop children's interest and activity;
- love your profession and children.

The teacher should be able to:

- effective, expressive speech and creative way of thinking;
- theoretical and practical preparation for specialization and pedagogical sciences;
- knowledge and skills of modern training technologies;
- national and universal values;
- pedagogical tact and technique;
- organization and a number of other pedagogical skills, etc.

Hundreds of researches and pedagogical experience show that a teacher should have the following moral qualities in order to incorporate them:

- objectivity;
- fairness;
- morality and spirituality;
- conviction;
- humanism;
- demandingness;
- sincerity;
- reputation;
- neatness, etc

In recent years, the professionalism and competence of teachers is often brought up. The concentration of professionalism and competence in the teacher is noted as the main signs of his pedagogical mastery and teacher innovation. It is no coincidence that the State Strategy for the development of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which was adopted in 2013 and envisages a long period until 2020, repeatedly emphasizes this issue and attaches great importance to it. The teacher's influence depends greatly on the teacher's academic skills, teaching experience and level of professionalism. There is a close connection between these

qualities of the teacher and the achievements of the students". Professionalism and competence are the basis of the teacher's activity structure. This problem, which occupies one of the main places in the education policy of our republic, is one of the issues that are emphasized in teacher training and teacher's professional activity. Cultivation of these qualities is relevant as one of the factors that ensure the efficiency, personality orientation and result orientation of pedagogical activity. Professionalism and competence of the teacher make the teaching profession more prestigious, teacher's work more interesting, more content and more efficient [6;91]

It's no secret that the low level of professionalism and competence of a number of teachers plays no small role in the decline of the teaching profession and teacher reputation. The teacher's professionalism and competence in his profession help students to read better, acquire deeper and more comprehensive knowledge, skills and habits in the educational process, acquire moral and ethical values more perfectly, become competitive specialists, educate every citizen as a worthy member of society, national and creates a favorable ground for their adoption of universal values. In recent years, a number of successful works have been carried out and are being carried out in the field of development of education, strengthening of its material and technical base, application of new information-communication and training technologies, increasing the qualifications and professionalism of teachers in our republic. In addition to these, there is a need to take new steps in order for the education system in the rapidly modernizing Republic of Azerbaijan to respond to the challenges of human capital development and to adapt the quality indicators of general education to European standards. In Azerbaijan education, there is a great demand for competent and professional teachers, teachers who deeply master new technologies, use them successfully in teaching, apply innovations and innovations to their own activities, are attached to school and their profession, consider teaching as their life's goal, literally breathe it. [8;39]

The educational reforms carried out in our republic, in addition to opening a wide path for pedagogical innovations, make it necessary to carry out innovations corresponding to European educational standards and apply innovations. Due to this necessity, increasing the level of professionalism and competence of teachers becomes one of the priority tasks of today. Mastering the pedagogical innovations taking place in the world, using them and deepening the content of the pedagogical activity by creating innovations is an urgent problem facing our education. Studying and applying pedagogical innovations existing in world education systems, as well as creating innovations by creative pedagogues and teachers, and applying them requires creative pedagogical thinking and initiative from teachers, so it is important to increase their level of professionalism and competence and bring innovations to their activities.

Improving the professional and professional training of teachers, their interest in innovation, constantly increasing their professional and professional

knowledge, skills and habits, engaging in self-education, self-education and pedagogical creativity is the basis of his formation as a professional and competent teacher. A teacher can become a professional teacher by not being satisfied with the knowledge he got at the university, the methodology he acquired and by constantly working on himself. Increasing the level of professionalism and competence of a teacher is a process directly related to his pedagogical activity. First of all, this is related to the fact that pedagogical activity itself is constantly in need of innovations. Pedagogical activity is a job that requires innovation. The speed of development of the society, the tendency of students to be more innovative, the training and educational activities conducted in the school require reconciliation with the growing demands of the society. In the school, in the lesson, the teacher should attract the students. Pupils should look forward to encountering something new every day, to gain new knowledge, and to be interested in going to school and interacting with teachers. It is the teachers who create it. Those teachers who are familiar with all the intricacies of the pedagogical process, not only do not get tired of working with students, but also enjoy this work, they live with school, lessons, and teaching. Students love them, respect them and are enthusiastic about their lessons. All this requires the teacher to constantly work on himself, improve his professionalism, expand his creative possibilities, and seek innovations. Earning the title of a professional and competent teacher is both an honor and a difficult task. Achieving this is possible only for those who are "born for this profession", who have innate ability and talent for teaching in a certain sense. Teachers who are persistently working to rise to the top of their profession, who are constantly searching, who are always looking for new things and who are innovative, who adopt new pedagogical thinking can be the owners of such a name. Just as this name elevates them, they also keep the teacher's name sacred, raise his reputation and increase interest and love for him.[1; 164]

In modern conditions, the main task of the school is to create an educational environment that contributes to the development of the student's personality. The professional competence of the teaching staff also plays an important role in solving this issue. Professional competence, which is a set of professional and personal qualities, is the theoretical and practical preparation of a teacher to perform pedagogical activities and determines his pedagogical mastery. A competent teacher builds his pedagogical activity at a high level and achieves stable results in the education of his students. The development of the professional competence of the teacher is the formation of his abilities to accept pedagogical innovations and to adapt to the changing pedagogical environment.[7;63]

The changes occurring in the modern education system require the teacher's improvement and professional development. Because only a teacher who thinks independently, can foresee the results of his activity, and models the educational process can be a grant to achieve the set goal. But how to develop the teacher's professional competence that meets today's require-

ments? For this, first of all, the teacher must have a desire to improve his professionalism. At the same time, favorable educational conditions and motivation for pedagogical development should be created. Such conditions that the teacher feels the need to improve the level of his pedagogical qualities.

A teacher can improve his pedagogical experience in various directions:

- In the professional field (knowledge of his subject).
- In the field of teaching methodology (adopting modern technologies, new methods and forms of training).

- In the field of pedagogical psychology. [10;145]

The teacher chooses the methodical topic for improvement according to his needs. He prepares a personal work plan according to the problem he has set in front of him based on the topic he has chosen. The teacher draws up a professional development plan taking into account the following directions:

- Study of psychological-pedagogical literature.
- Development of the program-methodical support of the educational process.
- Work on the subject of self-education.
- Participation in the methodical work system of the school.
- Use of professional development experience of other teachers.

Writing a plan is creative work. The implementation period of each activity provided for in the plan should be noted. The ways of realization of that plan are through the following activities:

- professional development system;
- self-education;
- to actively participate in methodological associations, pedagogical councils, seminars, conferences, master classes;
- to acquire modern educational technologies, methodical methods, pedagogical tools;
- master information and communication technologies;
- to participate in various competitions, projects, research works;
- generalization and dissemination of own experience, creation of publications. [9;53]

A teacher's participation in improvement courses refers to his after-school activities. It is important to increase the teacher's professionalism without leaving school activities. That is why it is necessary to improve the quality of the work carried out by methodical units in the school.

The goal of the methodical work in the school is to ensure the professional training of pedagogical workers in order to realize the tasks facing education by creating a continuous professional development system for each teacher. It is necessary to try to make the teacher the most active subject of the improvement process during methodical work. The most important thing in methodical work is to provide practical help to the teacher. The teacher should take any information related to his pedagogical activity from the methodical office, or he should have information about where he can take it.

Methodical work should be focused on the formation of a professional environment that develops the teacher. The task of methodical work is to create an educational environment that allows maximum realization of the potential of the pedagogical staff and students. Taking into account the modern demands placed on the teacher, the school determines the following ways of increasing the teacher's professionalism:

- Work in methodical combinations, creative or problem groups.
- Innovative activity of the teacher.
- Participation in professional mastery competitions, master classes, forums, festivals.
- Generalization and dissemination of personal pedagogical experience.
- Attestation of teachers, increasing their qualifications.
- Increasing professional competence with active forms of work.[15;162]

Training with teachers plays an important role in the formation of a developing professional environment. It is important to hold educational seminars and trainings in the school. Seminars are a form of theoretical training based on the learner's independent work with literature, extensive educational work.

Teachers evaluate the quality of the lessons according to the following indicators:

- Compliance with the age and individual capabilities of students;
- Forms of organization of student affairs;
- Having a connection with students' life activities;
- Innovation;
- Theoretical justification of practical activity.

Seminars-practicums are an effective form of work that enriches the knowledge and skills of teachers. It is also a source of information acquisition, training activities for systematization and improvement of knowledge, work on skill formation. Also, during the seminar, the issues of dissemination of pedagogical experience are discussed. For this reason, we attach great importance to seminars-practicums as an active form of methodical work conducted at school.

In the modern world, the dynamics of socio-economic and scientific-technical development make teachers' knowledge of new information technologies very relevant. In this regard, one of the important requirements for the teacher's pedagogical activity is the deep mastery of information and communication technologies.

Increasing professionalism in pedagogical activity should be a constant process. That is, the stages of increasing professional mastery should be repeated every time, but in a new quality. [13;119]

Self-education also plays a big role in increasing professionalism. Self-education is a qualitatively new form of mastering social practices.

A teacher preparing for a lesson, parent meeting, class time, school event, Olympiad needs to search for new information. Teaching is a creative profession. A teacher in search of innovation tries to make his work more interesting and lively. A teacher who teaches others must know more than those around him. Changes in the life of the society force the teacher to learn more. In

today's era, a teacher who is considered and selected has a greater reputation. The need to be a good teacher forces the teacher to work harder on himself. Evaluation of teacher's work, awarding of various names and awards depends on the teacher's mastery. It is possible to achieve them only through the improvement of knowledge and skills. [12; 143]

A teacher today should use forms and methods of increasing self-education and improvement through Internet resources and technologies. For this purpose, distance courses, distance conferences, distance seminars, distance competitions, distance Olympiads, and pedagogical forums can be organized for teachers.[5;211]

In short, a teacher who teaches every day must constantly learn. In this case, self-education is an important condition of a teacher's professional activity. The innovative activity of the teacher plays an important role in the process of professional self-improvement. Preparation for innovations is an important condition for his professional development. For this reason, creating a system of motivation and stimulation of the participants of innovative processes, providing an effective methodical organization of the activities of teachers applying innovations is the main part of the methodical work organized in the school. [2;94]

Listening and analyzing advanced practice lessons of colleagues, participation in master classes increases the teacher's professionalism. The analysis of the teacher's own lesson is also important: he sees the shortcomings in his work and tries to eliminate them. Analyzing one's own activity is a process of understanding pedagogical experience, overcoming difficulties at work, and stimulating self-improvement.

One of the main forms of increasing professional mastery is the dissemination of personal experience. Publication of articles, creation of personal professional sites and blogs is important for dissemination of pedagogical practice.[4;86]

A teacher's portfolio is an innovative form of methodical work and one of the methods of evaluating his professionalism. The portfolio demonstrates the most important results of the teacher's practical activity for the assessment of professional competence. Not only the results of the activity, but also the comparison with the previous results affects the development.

Scientific-theoretical novelty of research work.

In the teaching process, a systematic analysis of the implementation of the educational functions aimed at the expected results (the application of pedagogical activities and communication skills) of the educator was given, the attitude towards the paradigm was expressed, and thus the theoretical and technological bases of the implementation of the pedagogical functions aimed at the expected results were determined.

Practical significance of the research work.

Pedagogical mastery, in addition to mastering pedagogical technology at a high level, expresses the personality of the teacher as a whole, his experience, citizenship

and professional position. In this process, the availability of theoretical and technological bases related to the performance of educational functions aimed at the expected results (pedagogical activity and application of communication skills) improves the possibility of regulating the environment for the elimination of mistakes made in the activities of practical educators.

Result. 1) In the teaching process, the "system-structural" approach is a fruitful research option for revealing the nature of the teacher's pedagogical functions aimed at the expected results (pedagogical activity and communication skill application), forming generalizations; 2) It is convenient from a practical point of view to be based on the "opportunity-movement-new quality" paradigm in order to systematize the pedagogical functions of the educator (the application of pedagogical activity and communication skills) aimed at the expected results in the teaching process.

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